

MULTI-ACTOR PROPOSAL SUBMISSION IN 2025 HORIZON EUROPE CALLS

Factsheet

Focus

The European Commission Horizon Europe calls for Cluster 6 (Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment) and the Mission "A Soil Deal for Europe" are launched annually for the period 2021-2027, according to the published Work Programmes for each strand (Cluster 6 & Soil Mission). Most submissions finalized during September for the 2025 calls of each work programme. Using publicly available results on the number of submitted proposals under each topic, it is time to analyze these results in the 34 MA topics of the year.

Purpose

This factsheet provides a summary on the number of project proposals submitted to all MA topics of Cluster 6 and the Soil Mission in the 2025 Work Programme calls. Analyzing these data can be very useful to prioritize topic selection for future applications in 2026 or 2027.

Good to know

- ❑ A total of 639 proposals were submitted for MA topics in Cluster 6 (420 single stage, 219 two-stage), and 95 in Soil Mission (23 single stage, 72 two-stage), representing 45% and 66% of all submitted proposals for each CL6 and Soil Mission, respectively.
- ❑ On average (CL6+SOIL single-stage) 16,7 proposals were submitted with a high/low of 41 and 3 proposals (Figure 2). CL6+SOILS two-stage averaged 33,2 proposals/topic with high/low of 69/20 (Figure 1).
- ❑ Two-stage topics submit 10-page proposals on the first round, while a single stage is 30 (CSA) / 45 (RIA / IA) extension.
- ❑ The two-stage topics with the highest number of proposals were: 02-FARM2FORK-05 two-stage (69 proposals) - Developing agroecology living labs and lighthouses for climate action under the Food and Nutrition Security and Sustainable Agriculture (FNSSA) partnership, and 05-SOIL-02 two-stage (52 proposals) - Broadening the living labs approach for soil health in Africa and Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC)
- ❑ The topic with less participation was: 05-SOIL-01 two-stage (20 proposals) - Living Labs for soil remediation and green redevelopment of brownfields.

Figure 1: Number of proposals (scale 0 to 70) submitted to two-stage MA topics in Work Programme 2025. In yellow Soil Mission topics, in orange Cluster 6. PREMIERE own.

Figure 2: Number of proposals (scale 0 to +40) submitted to single-stage MA topics in Work Programme 2025. In yellow Soil Mission topics, in orange Cluster 6. PREMIERE own.

- The two single-stage topics with the highest number of proposals were both in F2F: 02-FARM2FORK-12 (41 proposals) - Nutrition and Mental Health, and 02-FARM2FORK-03 (37 proposals) - Overcoming the barriers for scaling up circular water management in agriculture.
- The two with lesser concurrence were in GOV: 03-GOVERNANCE-04 (4 proposals) - Operationalisation of bioeconomy sustainability principles, and 03-GOVERNANCE-13 (3 proposals) - Strengthening knowledge and skills of advisors and integrating them within Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) via an EU advisory network

Further information

- [Horizon Europe Cluster 6 webpage.](#)
- [Horizon Europe Soil Mission webpage.](#)

USEFUL TIP!

The data on the number of submissions per each Horizon topic is publicly available at the [EU Funding & Tenders Portal](#). Visit the Funding-Calls for proposals section and search for a call or topic acronym. After a call closes the Topic updates section of each topic displays the number of proposals submitted and the expected date for evaluation results.

About this factsheet and PREMIERE

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